

Innovative Multi-culm Bamboo Spatial Lattice Structure System

Xin Zhuo^{1,3}, Shenbin Zhang², Shilin Dong¹

1.College of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Zhejiang University, China. zhuoxin@zju.edu.cn

2.The Architectural Design & Research Institute of Zhejiang University Co. Ltd, China

3.Center for Balance Architecture, Zhejiang University, China

ABSTRACT

The multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure is proposed. The triangle is formed by connecting the end of three bamboo culms to each other by grouting joint. The structure is formed in the way of parallel connection between in-plane adjacent triangles. A freeform spatial lattice structure can be assembled simply by bolts in the site. The bearing capacity of the structure can be strengthened in the way of parallel connection between out-plane adjacent overlap triangles. The service life of the structure can be free from the dependence on the bamboo material's durability. The feasibility of the new structural system has been validated by a series of engineering practices.

KEYWORDS

bamboo culm, spatial lattice structure, structural relationship, extended longevity.

INTRODUCTION

Bamboo is an elegant, ecological, cheap building material. The bamboo culm mechanical properties are directional, with high axial strength as compared to mild steel, but weak in transverse direction [1]. The bamboo culm geometric characteristics are thin-wall, irregular cross-section, and tapered in a longitudinal direction. Neither can we change the diameter or thickness of culms, nor standardize their size. Thus, many advanced and mature technologies in timber structures are not suitable for bamboo culm structures.

There are dozens of types of joints for bamboo culm structures in the world [2]. Though about ten types of them are acceptable for spatial lattice structures [3], the cost of fabricating these types of joints and connecting the joint with bamboo culm is very high. High cost is unfavorable to the promotion of engineering applications. The public would rather choose solid wood, which is also a renewable material, than the troublesome hollow bamboo culm to build a house.

MULTI-CULM BAMBOO SPATIAL LATTICE STRUCTURE SYSTEM

To achieve simple manufacturing, convenient assembling, low cost, and reliable performance, we invented a new type of bamboo structural system which was named Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure by changing the relationship of culms from the conventional line link line into the innovative frame link frame [4]. This most important change will bring great convenience to manufacturing components in the factory and assembling the structure on site.

The composition of the new type of bamboo structure

Firstly, connect three bamboo culms head to tail to form a triangle frame as an assembling unit, as shown in Figure 1, then connect every adjacent bamboo frame unit in parallel to form a single-layer Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure.

Next, if each triangle is further connected to the top triangle in parallel, the stiffness and bearing capacity of the overlapped Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure can be strengthened. The more the number of the overlapped layers, the greater the structural stiffness, as shown in Figure 2. This structural system provides a new choice for a large-span bamboo culm structure. Due to the proposed structure still belongs to frame structure, the conventional connection joints, such as grout infilling and bolt, can be used.

Figure 1: The formation process of a Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure

The characteristics of the structure

- (1) In contrast to conventional line link line connection. By utilizing frame link frame connections, the original complicated three-dimensional spatial joints are simplified to two-dimensional production, which makes industrialization possible for manufacturing components of bamboo frame units.
- (2) The structure only needs two types of joints. The end joint connects the end of adjacent bamboo culms in one frame unit, and the parallel joint connects parallel adjacent bamboo culms. Both kinds of joints only need to connect two bamboo culms. This characteristic provides an adequate place to enhance the mechanical property of each joint.
- (3) Since any curved surface can be divided into a combination of multiple triangles in geometry, it is possible to use only two types of joint in the complex shape Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure. In the bamboo pavilion of this paper, we use the simplest kind of joint, the bolt, to a whole structure. The amount and the diameter of the bolts in a parallel joint can be selected according to the internal force of structural analysis.
- (4) The removal of one bamboo triangle frame will not affect the geometric invariance of the structure. Since the three adjacent bamboo triangle frames are still fixed in place by other triangle frames, as shown in Figure 3. It indicates that if we use the method of replacing the degraded triangle frame with a new one on site, the service life of the bamboo structure can be prolonged significantly and get rid of the dependence on the material durability of the bamboo culm.

Figure 2: Double-layer lattice structure

Figure 3: Replacing triangle

DESIGN OF THE BAMBOO PAVILION

The three centrosymmetric blooming petals architectural shape of the bamboo Pavilion designed for Beijing "2019 World Horticultural Exposition" is a hyperbolic paraboloid, as shown in Figure 4. It is a single-layer Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure, the height of the pavilion centre is 2.92m and the height of the eave is 3.41m, as shown in Figure 5. The open structure makes all the activities under it possible, which enables users to create their layout as shown in Figure 6 flexibly.

- (1) Diagram of the drainage system. The shape of the negative Gaussian curvature enables the rainwater to flow down to the ground via the valley line of the structure and avoid dropping directly from the eaves. The interlining of internal and external decorative surface layers uses coiled materials for waterproofing, as shown in figure 7 a.
- (2) Each layer of the roof. To provide a shelter from sunlight and rain, as well as thermal insulation, the inner decorative layer of bamboo mats, the waterproofing layer of coiled materials, and the external decorative layer of thatch were gradually assembled above the structure layer as shown in figure 7 b.

- (3) Bars. The structure was comprised of straight bamboo culms of 0.5-1.9 m long and 70-80 mm outer diameter. The Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure consists of 54 bamboo culm triangles. Of the nine kinds of triangle bamboo culm units, the largest size is 1.67×0.9 m and the smallest size is 0.8×0.5 m. The weight of each triangle unit was lighter than 14 kg.
- (4) Base. Because the weight of the bamboo structure is light and three footholds are weak in sensing the differential settlement, the three arch feet were fixed by three independent concrete bases with a cylinder of 0.4m deep and 0.5m in diameter.

Figure 4: Pavilion render

Figure 5: Pavilion size

a) Education

b) Office

c) Equipment

d) Recreation

Figure 6: Functions of the pavilion

a) Drainage system

b) Detail of roof layers

Figure 7: Roof design

COMPONENT FABRICATION AND STRUCTURAL ASSEMBLY

Component fabrication

Before the fabrication, the bamboo materials were treated with the technologies of insect prevention, mold proof and anti-corrosion to improve the durability of the materials. The bamboo culms were sawed according to the design lengths, and the two ends of each bamboo culm were sawed according to the design angles, as shown in Figure 8a. After the bamboo culms have been grouped, the corners of each triangle unit were temporarily fixed with tapes, and a 10 mm diameter hole used to grout was drilled in each corner of the triangle by an electric drill, as shown in Figure 8b. Finally, according to the design grouting length, cement mortar was infilled into the hole near the end-joint with a pneumatic grouting equipment.

Figure 8: Fabrication of triangles

Structural Assembly

In order to avoid the negative effects of savage assembly on the structure caused by accumulated errors, the sequence of assembly for the structure was from the structural centre to the edge instead of conventional method from bottom to top, as shown in Figure 9. The whole structure can be completed efficiently by using a simple tripod and a chain hoist without scaffolds.

Figure 9: Installation method from the structural centre to the edge

(1) *Installation of the First Block.* There are 30 triangle units in the first block of the roof of the structure. The first step was to assemble 6 triangle units in the center of the first block with temporary fasteners, according to the designed elevation. In the second step, each two adjacent bamboo culms were connected by two bolts. Finally, loosen the fasteners and continue to connect the remaining 24 triangle units according to the previous two steps until the first block as shown in Figure 10a was completed.

(2) *Installation for the Second Block.* There are 18 triangle units in the second block of the structure. The first step was to lift the first block to the designed elevation with a tripod and a chain hoist, and then assembled the second block according to the installation method of the first block, as shown in Figure 10b.

(3) *Installation for the Third Block.* There are 6 triangle units in the third block of the structure. The installation method of the third block was the same as that of the second block, as shown in Figure 10c.

(4) *Installation for the Bamboo Strips.* The final step of the assembly was to fix the bamboo strips criss-cross on the culms of the structure, which could strengthen structural stiffness and become a substructure for the inner decorative layer. The inner decorative layer of the bamboo mat, the waterproofing layer of flexible material, the external decorative layer of thatch, and electric wires of light were assembled, as shown in Figure 10 d.

Figure 10: Installation process

CONCLUSION

The engineering practice used the Multi-culm bamboo spatial lattice structure system has been constructed quickly and accurately, proving the feasibility and advancement of the new structural system and construction technology. It only took two days to assemble the structure and the roof. This petal-shaped pavilion used the cheap original bamboo culm as the structural member, and connections between the triangle units were all used by the ordinary bolts.

The new type of structural system can be easy to popularize to many countries and regions, because of the simple component fabrication, easy structural assembly, cheap connector, and the relatively good performance of the structure.

References

- [1] Villegas L., Morán R., García J.J., Combined culm-slat Guadua bamboo trusses. *Engineering Structures*, 2019; 184; 495–504.
- [2] Janssen J.J.A., International Bamboo and Rattan Organisation (INBAR) Technical Report 20: Designing and Building with Bamboo. *International Network for Bamboo and Rattan*, 2000.

- [3] Hong C.K., Li H.T., Lorenzo R., Wu G., Corbi I., Corbi O., Xiong Z.H., Yang D. and Zhang H.Z., Review on Connections for Original Bamboo Structures. *Journal of Renewable Materials*, 2019;7;713-730.
- [4] Zhuo X., Dong S.L., Bamboo multi-culm spatial lattice structure system and double-ring joint, 201710025356.4 [P]. *Invention patent(chinese)*, 2019.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful for the financial support of the National Major Science and Technology Projects of China (2017YFC0703500).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.